

Studies in Triethylamine-Water. Part-II. Conductance of Potassium Iodide in Triethylamine-Water Mixtures

S. THANGAVEL and MATHEW J. MOOLEL*

Department of Chemistry, Loyola College (Autonomous), Madras-600 034

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Triethylamine (Et_3N) is only partially miscible in water at room temperature. Conductance of potassium iodide is measured in Et_3N -water mixtures of compositions varying from 0.1 to 62 mole per cent of $\text{Et}_3\text{N}(\text{X}_t)$ at 15° and from 0.1 to 35 at 10° . The structure breaking nature of both K^+ and I^- in these solvent mixtures is observed. Hydration numbers of K^+ and I^- are obtained from the size parameter a_j as 8 and 3, respectively. The absence of association of the salt even in solvent mixtures of low dielectric constant is explained by the strong hydration of the ions in these solvent systems.

MANY studies are available in recent literature¹⁻¹² on the conductance of electrolytes in mixed solvents, which are miscible in all proportions at normal temperatures. This is not the case for solvent systems, which are only partially miscible at room temperatures, but form homogeneous solutions at higher or lower temperatures.

In the present work, we have measured the conductance of potassium iodide in triethylamine (Et_3N)-water mixtures. The binary solvent system has a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) at 18.3° . Potassium iodide was chosen as the electrolyte for this study because of its interesting behaviour towards the phase separation temperature (PST) of the binary solvent system^{13,14} salting-in at low composition (X_t) of Et_3N and salting-out at higher X_t .

Experimental

The laboratory reagent grade Et_3N (Sarabhai Merck) was purified by the method of Munney and Coetzee¹⁵, but for refluxing and distillation, sodium hydroxide was replaced by potassium hydroxide, since the latter is a more efficient dehydrating agent in this solvent¹⁶. The fraction distilling at temperatures between 89.0 and 89.5° was collected and used within 24 h after its purification. Purity of the sample was controlled through density, refractive index, assay analysis and by glc. Double-deionised water having specific conductance less than $1 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1}$ was used for all the measurements. $\text{KCl}(\text{A.R.}, \text{B.D.H.})$ was recrystallised twice from water, dried at 120° and used for standardisation of the conductance cell. Potassium iodide (G.R., Sarabhai Merck) was dried at 120° in an air oven and kept over fused CaCl_2 . The sample was used without further purification.

Measurements :

Since the solvent system is homogeneous in all proportions only below 18.3° and since many properties of the binary solvent mixtures are available in literature¹⁷⁻²¹ at 10 and 15° , all the measurements were made at those temperatures.

Conductance : A conductance cell was designed by modifying those used by Ablard and coworkers²² and Moolle and Schneider^{10,11}. The solvent mixtures of required compositions were prepared directly in the reservoir of the conductance cell by weighing one of the solvents and pipetting out the other. Small amounts of potassium iodide, weighed accurately, were introduced into the reservoir. The solutions were stirred with the aid of a magnetic stirrer, and a mercury column was used to transfer the solution from the reservoir to the cell. Measurements of conductance were made only after ensuring the temperature stability after thorough mixing of the solutions, confirmed by the constancy of the conductance reading. The cell constant was found to be $0.518 \pm 0.002 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The temperature was maintained at the desired values by an Ultra Cryostat MK 70 (VEB MLW Company, G.D.R.), which stabilised the temperature within $\pm 0.01^\circ$. A Wayne Kerr B642 Autobalance Universal Bridge which can measure the conductance between the range 1×10^{-1} to $1 \times 10^{-8} \Omega^{-1}$ within $\pm 0.2\%$ was used for the conductance measurements. The bridge was tested using standard resistances.

Conductance of potassium iodide was measured in Et_3N -water mixtures of compositions, expressed in mole percent of $\text{Et}_3\text{N} (\text{X}_t)$, equal to 0.1, 0.5, 0.9, 1.9, 3.3, 4.3, 7.1, 10.6, 15.1, 21.1, 29.3, 34.8, 41.6 and 61.6 at 15° , and 0.1, 4.3, 10.6, 21.1, 29.3 and 34.8 at 10° . The results are summarised in Table 1.

	$X_t = 41.6$			
3.454	5.024	-0.33		
6.910	4.732	0.11		
10.06	4.480	0.23		
13.73	4.274	0.24		
17.35	4.077	0.10		
20.43	3.962	-0.04		
23.48	3.838	-0.26		
	$X_t = 61.6$			
2.795	0.7032	-0.33		
4.168	0.6850	0.01		
5.932	0.6618	0.23		
7.687	0.6325	0.29		
9.917	0.6125	0.24		
11.78	0.5950	0.09		
13.42	0.5825	-0.07		
15.49	0.5645	-0.34		
	Temp. = 10°			
	$X_t = 0.1$			
10.14	104.1	0.13		
13.61	103.6	-0.01		
16.49	103.3	-0.05		
21.22	102.9	-0.06		
25.21	102.7	0.04		
38.44	101.7	-0.10		
53.02	101.0	-0.01		
67.76	100.3	-0.01		
83.09	99.7	0.04		
97.60	99.1	0.01		
	$X_t = 4.3$			
13.04	42.65	0.01		
16.19	42.49	0.01		
19.13	42.31	-0.06		
29.42	42.02	0.00		
39.65	41.77	0.05		
52.13	41.43	0.03		
64.69	41.10	-0.02		
65.31	40.88	-0.02		
	$X_t = 10.6$			
11.98	23.11	-0.01		
15.27	23.02	-0.01		
18.02	22.95	0.00		
20.89	22.88	0.00		
30.10	22.70	0.01		
38.23	22.56	0.01		
47.41	22.42	0.01		
56.66	22.31	0.02		
66.75	22.19	0.02		
76.00	22.06	-0.01		
85.11	21.96	-0.02		
	$X_t = 21.1$			
5.778	12.26	-0.10		
9.053	12.12	-0.05		
12.44	12.02	0.01		
15.67	11.91	0.02		
22.31	11.73	0.05		
32.08	11.50	0.06		
41.49	11.33	0.06		
51.84	11.16	0.04		
60.68	11.03	0.02		
70.25	10.88	-0.05		
80.77	10.79	-0.05		
	$X_t = 29.3$			
9.151	7.330	-0.14		
12.61	7.210	-0.04		
15.89	7.099	0.01		
20.63	6.980	0.07		
25.13	6.872	0.10		
35.40	6.660	0.06		
42.43	6.538	0.06		
51.11	6.397	0.07		
61.64	6.243	-0.18		

(Contd. Table 1)

	$X_t = 34.8$	
5.219	5.613	-0.12
9.223	5.412	0.02
12.48	5.293	0.08
15.12	5.202	0.09
19.85	5.051	0.05
25.25	4.838	-0.11

C = Concentration of KI in molarity, Λ = equivalent conductance in $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ equiv.}^{-1}$, $\Delta \Lambda = \Lambda$ (theoretical) - Λ (experimental), X_t = Mole percent of Et_3N in water.

Transport numbers : Hittorf transport numbers of the iodide ion were determined at 10 and at 15° in solvent mixtures of X_t equal to 0.1, 0.9, 1.9, 3.3, 4.3 and 7.1. Since the conductance of potassium iodide is poor beyond this mole per cent of Et_3N , measurements were not extended to higher compositions.

Dielectric constant : Dielectric constants of the solvent mixtures, not available in literature, were measured at compositions X_t equal to 21.6, 29.3, 34.8, 41.6, and 61.6 at 10 and at 15°. The measurements were not made for $X_t < 20$, since considerable conductance of the solvent mixtures in that region interfered with the accurate determination of dielectric constant. The instrument used was a Franz Kustner Nacht KG Dresden DK Meter 6K and was standardised using liquids of known dielectric constants.

Results

Et_3N behaves like a weak electrolyte in water²³. The solvent conductances are subtracted from those of the electrolytic solutions to get the salt conductances. The properties of the solvent mixtures, needed for the analysis of the conductance data, are given in Table 2. The values of the dielectric constants are from our own measurements and are extrapolated to the value for pure water for the region $X_t < 20$. There is no appreciable difference in these values at 10 and 15°.

The data of the conductance measurements (Table 1) were analysed using Fuoss-Onsager equation²⁴ with three parameters namely, Λ_0 (the conductance at infinite dilution), $J(a)$ where a_j is a size parameter, and K_A (the association constant); and the equation with two parameters only, namely, Λ_0 and $J(a)$.

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 - S(C\gamma)^{\frac{1}{2}} + EC\gamma \ln(6E_1 C\gamma) + JC\gamma - K_A \Lambda C\gamma f^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 - SC^{\frac{1}{2}} + EC \ln(6E_1 C) + JC \quad (2)$$

The terms involved in these equations have their usual significance²⁴. The results were processed using a computer programme to get Λ_0 , K_A and the size parameter a_j from $J(a)$.

Association of potassium iodide : The association constant using equation (1) comes out to be negative. This has no physical significance. The experimental slopes are smaller than their theoretical values indicating the absence of association of the

TABLE 2—SOLVENT PROPERTIES OF Et₃N-WATER MIXTURES

X _t	Density g cm ⁻³		Viscosity (η) P		Dielectric constant 10°/15°	Specific conductance × 10 ⁸ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
	10°	15°	10°	15°		10°	15°
0.10	0.9988	0.9985	0.0137	0.0120	81.5	77.94	92.34
0.50	—	0.9935	—	0.0139	81.0	—	175.8
0.90	—	0.9875	—	0.0150	79.5	—	194.8
1.90	—	0.9775	—	0.0215	77.0	—	171.1
3.30	—	0.9640	—	0.0260	73.5	—	119.6
4.30	0.9678	0.0565	0.0390	0.0310	71.0	76.23	95.65
7.10	—	0.9340	—	0.0425	63.0	—	46.79
10.6	0.9160	0.9110	0.0640	0.0480	54.0	14.26	19.33
15.1	—	0.8875	—	0.0475	42.0	—	6.018
21.1	0.8635	0.8570	0.0540	0.0405	30.0	0.988	1.445
29.3	0.8350	0.8275	0.0400	0.0305	19.0	0.327	0.473
34.8	0.8208	0.8140	0.0305	0.0205	15.0	0.145	0.212
41.6	—	0.8010	—	0.0185	10.0	—	0.109
61.6	—	0.7705	—	0.0085	7.0	—	0.015

TABLE 3—RESULTS OF CONDUCTANCE STUDIES

X _t	Λ ₀ Ω ⁻¹ cm ² equiv ⁻¹	S _e *	S ₀ **	J(a)	a _J (Å)	λ ₀ ⁺	λ ₀ ⁻	Λ ₀ η	λ ₀ ⁺ η	λ ₀ ⁻ η	r _λ ⁺ (Å)	r _λ ⁻ (Å)
0.1	113.79±0.08	24.5	70.80	450±16	169	50.30	63.49	1.37	0.604	0.762	1.36	1.08
0.5	99.97±0.06	21.7	61.85	378±13	38	44.19	55.78	1.39	0.614	0.775	1.33	1.06
0.9	88.53±0.09	20.5	57.28	325±14	19	39.13	49.40	1.33	0.587	0.741	1.40	1.11
1.9	70.91±0.07	15.9	43.36	257±10	15	31.34	39.57	1.52	0.674	0.851	1.22	0.96
3.3	58.96±0.06	24.4	37.50	246±10	21	26.07	32.91	1.53	0.678	0.856	1.21	0.96
4.3	52.35±0.03	10.1	29.84	201±8	67	23.14	29.21	1.62	0.717	0.906	1.14	0.91
7.1	38.64±0.03	10.3	27.37	221±8	35	17.08	21.56	1.64	0.726	0.916	1.13	0.90
10.6	28.90±0.03	11.2	25.99	200±9	13±0.3	12.77	16.13	1.39	0.613	0.794	1.34	1.06
15.1	20.38±0.03	12.8	28.34	223±11	7.8±0.4	9.01	11.37	0.97	0.428	0.540	1.92	1.52
21.1	15.55±0.03	26.6	37.78	277±20	6.7±0.4	6.87	8.68	0.63	0.278	0.352	2.95	2.33
29.3	10.96±0.06	31.0	58.75	458±35	6.8±0.3	4.84	6.12	0.33	0.148	0.187	5.55	4.39
34.8	9.00±0.08	34.0	76.17	621±47	7.1±0.3	3.98	5.02	0.23	0.100	0.126	8.24	6.53
41.6	7.76±0.27	41.0	124.2	636±146	6.8±0.4	3.43	4.33	0.14	0.063	0.080	12.9	10.2
61.6	4.20±0.35	4.3	254.1	4027±358	8.9±1.0	1.86	2.34	0.04	0.019	0.016	58.0	41.2
Temp. = 10°												
0.1	106.14±0.04	72.6	64.48	14±7	0.9±0.1	46.81	59.33	1.45	0.641	0.813	1.28	1.01
4.3	43.72±0.03	34.8	27.50	-376±6	0.8±0.1	19.28	24.44	1.71	0.752	0.953	1.09	0.86
10.6	23.88±0.01	20.0	20.79	56±2	3.1±0.1	10.53	13.35	1.53	0.674	0.854	1.22	0.96
21.1	13.14±0.03	22.0	30.34	130±7	4.1±0.1	5.79	7.35	0.70	0.313	0.397	2.62	2.07
29.3	8.94±0.08	22.5	46.71	233±19	5.3±0.2	3.94	5.00	0.36	0.158	0.200	5.20	4.10
34.8	7.12±0.11	22.0	62.6	493±58	7.0±0.5	3.14	3.98	0.22	0.096	0.121	8.54	6.78

* Slope of \sqrt{C} vs Λ plots. ** Calculated Onsager slope.

electrolyte. The results obtained from equation (2) are given in Table 3.

Variation of λ₀ with X_t: The limiting conductance of the salt Λ₀ shows a monotonic decrease with increase in X_t, while the Walden products show maximum near the solvent composition of X_t=5.5 (Fig. 1). The transport number of iodide ion remains constant with respect to X_t within the limits of experimental error in the range of solvent compositions studied. The values are 0.558 and 0.559 at 15 and 10°, respectively. Λ₀ values are split up into the ionic values using the transport numbers at their constant values. λ₀ values of both K⁺ and I⁻ ions show a monotonic decrease with X_t at both temperatures. Their Walden products also show maximum at the same solvent composition of X_t=5.5 (Fig. 1).

Since the ionic radii r_λ, obtained from Walden products, are initially smaller than the crystal radii r_c, no physical significance can be given to them.

Their values increase with X_t in general, and are controlled by the variation of Walden products. Similar results have been obtained by several authors in other systems²⁴⁻²⁷.

Variation of a_J: The size parameter, obtained from J-terms, are of large values when X_t<20. It decreases⁴ and stabilises to a constant value of 7 Å when X_t>20 (Table 3).

Discussion

Structural effects: Structural effects play a part in this system. Where there is a viscosity maximum in the solvent mixture and it does not control the course of the λ₀ with X_t, structural effects in the solvent system are at work. Examples are HCl, CH₃COOH, CH₃COONa and KCl in ethanol-Water^{5,6}, and HCl and NaCl in propan-1-ol-water^{7,8}. From a similar behaviour, we conclude that both K⁺ and I⁻ in this solvent system Et₃N-water, influence the structure of water.

Fig. 1. Variation of limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) and Walden product ($\Lambda_0 r_a$) of KI with solvent composition (X_t): (\square, \blacksquare) 10° and (\circ, \bullet) 15° .

Values of the ionic radius r_a , smaller than the crystal radius r_0 , obtained from Walden product indicate that the ions destroy the structure of water²⁸. This is true in the present case. Walden products, which are large in magnitude and have a negative temperature coefficient show structure-breaking of water^{12,20}. This also is verified here (Table 3). We conclude that these two ions, K^+ and I^- are structure-breakers of water in this solvent system, with their maximum effect in about 5.5 mole per cent of Et_3N in which the Walden products have their maxima for these ions. This approach is used below for the elucidation of the hydration of the salt in the aqueous solvent mixtures.

Hydration numbers : Since Et_3N can interact with ions only with its lone pair of electrons, it can solvate the cations. We rule out the selective solvation of K^+ by Et_3N , from solubility study²⁰ and from the study of solvent transport numbers²¹. We, therefore, consider that both the ions are preferentially hydrated.

The constant value of a_j (when $X_t > 20$) is split up into the ionic values using the transport numbers. The transport number is inversely proportional to the radius of the ion as per Stokes law. When the stabilised value of a_j , namely, 7 \AA is split up into the ionic values, the radii of K^+ and I^- are 3.91 and 3.09 \AA , respectively. The hydration number (n_h) of these ions are now calculated by the formula,

$$n_h = 4\pi(r^3 - r_0^3)/3V_w \quad (3)$$

The volume of a water molecule in the liquid state (V_w) is taken to be 30 \AA^3 as recommended by Robinson and Stokes²². The hydration numbers of K^+ and I^- come out to be 8 and 3, respectively and remain constant over the entire composition range

$X_t > 20$ of Et_3N in water. Hydration numbers in water given in literature²³ for the potassium ion vary from 2 to 74 (from transport number) and 5 to 7 (from conductance), the corresponding values for the iodide ion are 2 (transport number) and 2 to 2.5 (conductance).

It is now not surprising to see the absence of association even in Et_3N -water mixtures of low dielectric constant in which association could have been expected. This could be understood from the high degree of hydration of potassium and iodide ions in these solvent mixtures which hinders the association of the ions.

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